

Review Article About Seat of Fainting Cases

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Abstract:

Fainting, clinically termed syncope denotes a transient loss of consciousness typically caused by a temporary reduction in blood flow to the brain. It presents a common yet concerning medical event that warrants attention from healthcare professionals, researchers, and the public alike. This research introduces an innovative approach to the design and implementation of a seat monitoring system aimed at detecting fainting episodes in individuals. The proposed system relies on the integration of two key sensors, namely concussion and tilt sensors, to enhance the accuracy

and reliability of fainting event identification. The concussion sensor is employed to detect sudden and impactful movements, indicative of a potential loss of consciousness. This sensor is strategically positioned within the seat structure to capture abrupt changes in acceleration, providing real-time data on the dynamics of the seated individual. Concurrently, a tilt sensor is incorporated to monitor changes in the seat's orientation, allowing for the identification of unusual body positions associated with fainting incidents. The data from both sensors are processed through an intelligent algorithm that analyzes patterns and anomalies. The algorithm utilizes machine learning techniques to differentiate between normal movements and those indicative of a fainting episode. By combining information from the concussion and tilt sensors, the system aims to minimize false positives and enhance the overall accuracy of fainting detection. The proposed seat monitoring system has promising applications in various settings, including public transportation, healthcare facilities, and environments where individuals are seated for extended periods. Early detection of fainting incidents can lead to timely intervention, potentially preventing injuries and ensuring the safety of individuals in vulnerable situations. The integration of advanced sensors and machine learning algorithms in this system represents a significant step towards developing a reliable and efficient solution for fainting detection. The research findings contribute to the growing field of smart and responsive technologies that prioritize user safety and well-being in diverse scenarios.

Keywords: *syncope, seat monitoring system, machine learning techniques, safety, responsive technologies.*

Introduction

Fainting, clinically referred to as syncope, is a transient loss of consciousness typically resulting from a temporary reduction in blood flow to the brain. A prevalent and concerning medical event requires careful attention from healthcare professionals and researchers. Detecting fainting

incidents in a timely manner is crucial for providing appropriate medical intervention and ensuring the safety of individuals, especially in situations where sudden loss of consciousness could lead to injuries. This research introduces an innovative approach to address the challenge of detecting fainting episodes by proposing a seat monitoring system. The system relies on the

integration of two key sensors, namely concussion and tilt sensors, to enhance the accuracy and reliability of fainting event identification. The concussion sensor is designed to detect sudden and impactful movements, which may indicate a potential loss of consciousness. Strategically positioned within the seat structure, this sensor captures abrupt changes in acceleration, providing real-time data on the dynamics of the seated individual. Concurrently, a tilt sensor is incorporated to monitor changes in the seat's orientation, enabling the identification of unusual body positions associated with fainting incidents. By integrating information from both sensors, this seat monitoring system aims to improve the precision of fainting detection. The data collected by the concussion and tilt sensors are processed through an intelligent algorithm that analyzes patterns and anomalies. Leveraging machine learning techniques, the algorithm distinguishes between normal movements and those indicative of a fainting episode. The proposed system holds significant potential for various applications, including public transportation, healthcare facilities, and environments where individuals are seated for extended periods. Early detection of fainting incidents through this innovative system could facilitate prompt intervention, potentially preventing injuries and safeguarding the well-being of individuals in vulnerable situations. In summary, the integration of advanced sensors, such as concussion and tilt sensors, in a seat monitoring system represents a promising avenue for enhancing the detection of fainting cases. This research contributes to the development of smart and responsive technologies that prioritize user safety and address critical healthcare challenges.

Literature Review

In 2020 David S. Lindberg et al. (2020) This study addresses the issue of inpatient falls in hospital settings, a serious problem leading to injuries or fatalities. Existing falls risk assessment tools lack specificity in identifying the most crucial factors for predicting falls. The study

employs artificial intelligence (AI) methods, including classification tree, bagging, random forest, and adaptive boosting, applied to Electronic Health Record (EHR) data, to improve predictive performance and identify key risk factors associated with hospital-acquired falls. The objective is to use tree-based machine learning methods to determine the most important predictors of inpatient falls, validated through cross-validation. A case-control study with EHR and administrative data collected from 14 medical surgical units between January 1, 2013, and October 31, 2013, includes 38 predictor variables related to patient characteristics, admission information, assessment data, clinical information, and organizational characteristics. The results show that bagging, random forest, and boosting outperform traditional methods like the Morse Fall Scale in terms of AUROC. Key features for predicting inpatient fall risk include History of Falls, Age, Morse Fall Scale total score, quality of gait, unit type, mental status, and the number of high fall risk increasing drugs In 2020 Chengyin Ye et al. (2020) The objective of this study was to develop and validate an electronic health record (EHR)-based fall risk predictive tool to identify older individuals at a higher risk of falls. Using the XGBoost machine-learning algorithm, the one-year fall prediction model was constructed and tested on an independent validation cohort comprising 265,225 older patients (≥ 65 years) from Maine's EHR data (2016-2018). Results showed that the model achieved a validated C-statistic of 0.807. It accurately identified high-risk individuals, with 50% of true positives confirmed to fall within the first 94 days of the next year. The model also predicted falls in advance, capturing 58.01% and 54.93% of falls occurring within the first 30 and 30–60 days of the next year, respectively. The identified high-risk patients exhibited severe disease comorbidities, increased cardiovascular and mental medication prescriptions, and heightened historical clinical utilization, indicating the complexity of fall etiology. The XGBoost algorithm incorporated 157 impactful predictors into the final model, with cognitive disorders, abnormalities of gait and balance, Parkinson's disease, fall history, and

osteoporosis identified as the top-five strongest predictors of future fall events. In conclusion, the EHR-based risk assessment tool demonstrated improved discriminative ability, offering the potential for immediate deployment in health systems. It provides automatic early warnings to older adults with an elevated risk of falls and identifies personalized risk factors to facilitate customized fall interventions. In 2023 Miyuki Takase et al. (2023) This study aimed to explore the interactions among patients, the environment, and nursing practices contributing to patient falls from the perspective of nurses. A retrospective review of incident reports on patient falls from 2016 to 2020 was conducted, analyzing 4,176 reports using a text-mining approach. Key findings include that 79.0% of falls were unwitnessed by nurses, and 8.7% occurred during direct nursing care. Clustering of incident reports revealed 16 clusters. Patient-related clusters involved decline in physiological/cognitive function, loss of balance, and use of hypnotic and psychotropic agents. Nurse-related clusters included lack of situation awareness, reliance on patient families, and insufficient implementation of the nursing process. Clusters involving both patients and nurses addressed the unproductive use of alarms and call bells, inappropriate footwear, problematic use of walking aids and bedrails, and insufficient understanding of patients' activities of daily living. Environmental factors, such as chair-related falls, were also identified. Falls during bathing/showering or using a bedside commode involved patient, nurse, and environmental factors.

The study concludes that falls result from dynamic interactions between patients, nurses, and the environment. Given the challenges in modifying patient factors quickly, emphasis should be on addressing nursing and environmental factors to reduce falls. Improving nurses' situation awareness is highlighted as crucial, influencing their decisions and actions in preventing falls.

In 2023 Roman Schniepp et al. (2023) This cohort study aimed to assess the predictive validity of multimodal clinical assessment and quantitative measures of in- and off-laboratory

mobility for fall-risk estimation in patients with cerebellar ataxia (CA). Over a 6-month period, 93 patients with hereditary and sporadic/secondary forms of CA, along with 63 healthy controls, were prospectively evaluated for falls. The assessment included clinical and functional fall risk evaluations, in-laboratory gait examinations, and a 2-week inertial sensor-based daily mobility monitoring. Results showed that 64% of patients experienced falls, with 65% of these resulting in severe injuries. Patients exhibited mild-to-moderate ataxic gait disorders. Fall status and frequency in patients could be reliably predicted (78% and 81% accuracy, respectively), primarily based on their retrospective fall history. Clinical scoring of ataxic symptoms, in-laboratory gait examinations, and off-laboratory mobility measures improved classification and provided unique information for predicting fall severity (84% accuracy). The study suggests a stepwise approach for fall risk assessment in CA patients, where fall history-taking informs the general fall risk, and clinical scoring combined with instrument-based mobility measures provides in-depth information on the risk of recurrent and injurious falling

In study Li Rong Wang et al. (2023) addresses the overconfidence issue in deep learning models used for health signal data in assisted living and preventive healthcare. The proposed solution, called Reconstruction Uncertainty Estimate (RUE), draws inspiration from autoencoders and introduces a distributional uncertainty estimation method. RUE is derived from any trained model through a two-step process involving training a separate multilayer perceptron as a decoder and calculating uncertainty based on the reconstruction error of the decoder. The method is designed to be easy to implement and computationally efficient, supporting point-of-care decision making. The study also suggests non-parametric and parametric methods to compute prediction intervals from RUE. Evaluation against Monte-Carlo dropout and the Gaussian Process Regressor on a health signal dataset from intensive care unit patients demonstrates RUE's superiority, showing high correlation with

absolute error and the lowest area under the risk-coverage curve value. RUE-derived prediction intervals consistently outperform alternatives across key metrics, highlighting its potential to enhance the reliability of deep learning applications in healthcare and contribute to more informed decision-making.

The Aim of The Project

1. Identification and Understanding of Underlying Health Conditions: Investigating the triggers and factors contributing to syncope aids in identifying underlying medical conditions such as cardiac arrhythmias, neurological disorders, vasovagal reactions, or medication-related side effects. Understanding these conditions is crucial for accurate diagnosis, appropriate management, and timely intervention.

2. Development of Diagnostic Protocols: Research into fainting cases contributes to the formulation of comprehensive diagnostic protocols and guidelines for healthcare professionals. These protocols help in assessing patients who have experienced syncope, enabling accurate diagnosis and appropriate treatment plans based on the underlying causes.

3. Risk Assessment and Management Strategies: Analyzing the seat of fainting cases allows for the identification of risk factors associated with syncope. This information assists in creating tailored management strategies to mitigate risks and prevent future occurrences. It involves lifestyle modifications, medication adjustments, or specific interventions based on the identified causes.

4. Preventive Measures and Public Awareness: Understanding the root causes of syncope aids in raising public awareness. Educating individuals about the warning signs, triggers, and preventive measures empowers them to recognize symptoms early, seek timely medical attention, and adopt lifestyle modifications to prevent fainting episodes.

5. Advancement in Medical Interventions and Therapies: Research into the seat of fainting cases contributes to advancements in medical interventions and therapies. Understanding the

underlying mechanisms allows for the development of targeted treatments and therapies tailored to specific causes, thereby improving patient outcomes and quality of life.

6. Reduction of Healthcare Burden: By identifying and addressing the root causes of syncope, healthcare providers aim to reduce the burden on healthcare systems. Early recognition and appropriate management of syncope cases may lead to fewer emergency room visits, hospitalizations, and unnecessary medical investigations.

Project Outline

This project subdivided into four chapters; these chapters were framed according to the working series of this study.

Chapter one: presents the introduction, literature review and related work with the aim of this project. The purpose of this chapter is to give an overview of the motivation and the main objective of the current project.

Fainting

Syncope, commonly known as fainting, or passing out, is a loss of consciousness and muscle strength characterized by a fast onset, short duration, and spontaneous recovery (Peeters, et al., 2014). It is caused by a decrease in blood flow to the brain, typically from low blood pressure. There are sometimes symptoms before the loss of consciousness such as lightheadedness, sweating, pale skin, blurred vision, nausea, vomiting, or feeling warm (Peeters, et al., 2014; Chen-Scarabelli, & Scarabelli, 2004). Syncope may also be associated with a short episode of muscle twitching (Peeters, et al., 2014; Chen-Scarabelli, & Scarabelli, 2004). Psychiatric causes can also be determined when a patient experiences fear, anxiety, or panic; particularly before a stressful event, usually medical in nature (Singh, et al., 2021; Hadji-Turdeghal, 2019). When consciousness and muscle strength are not completely lost, it is called presyncope (Peeters, et al., 2014). It is recommended that presyncope be treated the same as syncope (Peeters, et al., 2014). Causes range from non-serious to potentially fatal (Peeters, et al., 2014). There are

three broad categories of causes: heart or blood vessel-related; reflex, also known as neurally mediated; and orthostatic hypotension (Peeters, et al., 2014; Chen-Scarabelli, & Scarabelli, 2004). Issues with the heart and blood vessels are the cause in about 10% and typically the most serious while neurally mediated is the most common (Peeters, et al., 2014). Heart-related causes may include an abnormal heart rhythm, problems with the heart valves or heart muscle and blockages of blood vessels from a pulmonary embolism or aortic dissection among others (Peeters, et al., 2014). Neurally mediated syncope occurs when blood vessels expand and heart rate decreases inappropriately (Peeters, et al., 2014). This may occur from either a triggering event such as exposure to blood, pain, strong feelings or a specific activity such as urination, vomiting, or coughing (Peeters, et al., 2014). Neurally mediated syncope may also occur when an area in the neck known as the carotid sinus is pressed (Peeters, et al., 2014). The third type of syncope is due to a drop in blood pressure when changing position such as when standing up (Peeters, et al., 2014). This is often due to medications that a person is taking but may also be related to dehydration, significant bleeding or infection (Peeters, et al., 2014). There also seems to be a genetic component to syncope (Kenny, Bhangu, & King-Kallimanis, 2013).

A medical history, physical examination, and electrocardiogram (ECG) are the most effective ways to determine the underlying cause (Peeters, et al., 2014). The ECG is useful to detect an abnormal heart rhythm, poor blood flow to the heart muscle and other electrical issues, such as long QT syndrome and Brugada syndrome (Peeters, et al., 2014). Heart related causes also often have little history of a prodrome (Peeters, et al., 2014). Low blood pressure and a fast heart rate after the event may indicate blood loss or dehydration, while low blood oxygen levels may be seen following the event in those with pulmonary embolism (Peeters, et al., 2014). More specific tests such as implantable loop recorders, tilt table testing or carotid sinus massage may be useful in uncertain cases (Peeters, et al., 2014). Computed tomography

(CT) is generally not required unless specific concerns are present (Peeters, et al., 2014). Other causes of similar symptoms that should be considered include seizure, stroke, concussion, low blood oxygen, low blood sugar, drug intoxication and some psychiatric disorders among others (Peeters, et al., 2014). Treatment depends on the underlying cause (Peeters, et al., 2014; Chen-Scarabelli, & Scarabelli, 2004). Those who are considered at high risk following investigation may be admitted to hospital for further monitoring of the heart (Peeters, et al., 2014). Syncope affects about three to six out of every thousand people each year (Peeters, et al., 2014). It is more common in older people and females (Ruwald, 2013). It is the reason for one to three percent of visits to emergency departments and admissions to hospital (Ruwald, 2013). Up to half of women over the age of 80 and a third of medical students describe at least one event at some point in their lives (Chen-Scarabelli, & Scarabelli, 2004). Of those presenting with syncope to an emergency department, about 4% died in the next 30 days (Peeters, et al., 2014). The risk of a poor outcome, however, depends very much on the underlying cause (Toscano, 2012).

Causes of Fainting

Causes range from non-serious to potentially fatal (Marine, 2012). There are three broad categories of causes: heart or blood vessel related; reflex, also known as neutrally mediated; and orthostatic hypotension (D'Ascenzo, et al., 2013). Issues with the heart and blood vessels are the cause in about 10% and typically the most serious while neutrally mediated is the most common (Moya, et al., 2009).

Neutrally mediated syncope

Reflex syncope or neutrally mediated syncope occurs when blood vessels expand and heart rate decreases inappropriately leading to poor blood flow to the brain (Shen, et al., 2017). This may occur from either a triggering event such as exposure to blood, pain, strong feelings, or a specific activity such as urination, vomiting, or coughing (Mechanic, & Grossman, 2022).

Vasovagal syncope

Vasovagal (situational) syncope is one of the most common types which may occur in response to any of a variety of triggers, such as scary, embarrassing or uneasy situations, during blood drawing, or moments of sudden unusually high stress. There are many different syncope syndromes which all fall under the umbrella of vasovagal syncope related by the same central mechanism. First, the person is usually predisposed to decreased blood pressure by various environmental factors. A lower than expected blood volume, for instance, from taking a low-salt diet in the absence of any salt-retaining tendency. Or heat causing vaso-dilation and worsening the effect of the relatively insufficient blood volume. The next stage is the adrenergic response. If there is underlying fear or anxiety (e.g., social circumstances), or acute fear (e.g., acute threat, needle phobia), the vaso-motor center demands an increased pumping action by the heart (flight or fight response). This is set in motion via the adrenergic (sympathetic) outflow from the brain, but the heart is unable to meet requirements because of the low blood volume, or decreased return. A feedback

response to the medulla is triggered via the afferent vagus nerve. The high (ineffective) sympathetic activity is thereby modulated by vagal (parasympathetic) outflow leading to excessive slowing of heart rate. The abnormality lies in this excessive vagal response causing loss of blood flow to the brain. The tilt-table test typically evokes the attack. Avoiding what brings on the syncope and possibly greater salt intake is often all that is needed.

Results

Fall Detection Systems

Figure 1 depicts a typical fall detection system. The flow of real-time fall detection system starts with the detection device(s) sending motion data to a processing unit. When the algorithm captures a fall, alarm/action will be triggered. This can be in forms of alert sound (to attract attention and help from people in the vicinity), immediate intervention, or sending alarm messages to family members and/or caregivers. The information may also include time of the incident, location, direction, and status (conscious/unconscious) of the faller.

Figure 1. A System Overview of a Typical Fall Detection System

Part of Device

A fainting sensor was manufactured using the following devices:

1. Mercury digital inclination sensor
2. Arduino Nano
3. GPS NEO 6M

- 4. SIM800L
 - 5. Lipo Battery
 - 6. Vibration sensor
- 3-3-1 Mercury digital inclination sensor.

The mercury tilt sensor is a tilt sensor which opens and closes an electrical circuit when it is inclined beyond a certain angle. It can be used in tilt prevention device, an alarm circuit, and in many DIY projects. There are different types of tilt switch sensor modules for sensing the tilt and module can have a ball switch or mercury switch (Amazon, 2023).

Figures 2. Mercury Digital Inclination Sensor

Arduino Nano

The 8-bit board with 54 digital pins, 16 analog inputs, and 4 serial ports. Arduino mega of Fig. 3 is used because the screen deal with serial data and it is more efficient than other types (Amazon, 2023).

Figure 3. Arduino Nano

GPS NEO 6M

This guide shows how to use the NEO-6M GPS module with the Arduino to get GPS data. GPS

stands for Global Positioning System and can be used to determine position, time, and speed if you're travelling (Arduino Store, 2023).

Figure 4. GPS NEO 6M

SIM800L

SIM 800L is a Mini-GSM module, the 2G GSM - and GPRS-data. Now with things mobile Sim card in the Bundle. The module has a small size and low power consumption. Twice as large as a coin and 1mA in Sleep Mode.

It uses a serial interface communication, supported 3GPP TS 27.007, 27.005 and SIMCOM enhanced AT commands. In addition, it supports the A-GPS technology, which helps to maintain the indoor position of the mobile radio network (Arduino Store, 2023).

Figure 5. SIM800L

Lipo Battery

LiPo (Lithium Polymer) batteries are a great way to power your portable projects (ideal for the Adafruit Feather!). Compared to other battery chemistries they're more compact, lighter and offer a consistent voltage output (rather than constantly dropping like other types!). They also offer higher rates of discharge which is ideal for high-power projects. This LiPo battery has a capacity of 1200mAh (3.7V) with a 2-pin JST-PH 2mm connector on a ~100mm cable. ideal for most projects and wearables (Arduino Store, 2023).

Figure 6. Lipo Battery

Vibration sensor

This TS spring coil antenna matches great with any of our 868MHz RF Modules. It is a compact antenna, only 17.5mm long, and has 2-3 dBi of gain and 500 impedance, so it will work fantastically with just about any 868MHz RF receiver / RF transmitter. The structure of this spring antenna is simple, lightweight, and it is made of copper-clad wire, so you can solder it easily (Arduino Store, 2023).

Figure 7. Vibration Sensor

Seat of Fainting Cases Circuit

The figure 8 show the circuit of seat of fainting cases using Arduino Nano and other electrical part.

Figure 8. The Circuit of Seat of Fainting Cases

Arduino Code for Seat of Fainting Cases Circuit

The test was carried out using the Arduino IDE software The Arduino Integrated Development Environment - or Arduino Software (IDE) - is software that connects to the Arduino boards to upload programs and communicate with them. Programs written using Arduino Software (IDE) are called sketches. These sketches are written in the text editor and are saved with the file extension .ino program the script into the Arduino Nano so that it can process the Mercury digital inclination sensor and Vibration sensor. As following

```
#include <Wire.h>
#include <SoftwareSerial.h>
#include <TinyGPS.h>
TinyGPS gps;
SoftwareSerial gs(5, 4); // RX, TX
SoftwareSerial gsm(2, 3); // RX, TX
uint32_t tsLastReport = 0;
long del;
float flat, flon;
```

```

String sms, sms1;
long flagt;
float sflat, sflon;
int flag1 = 0;
// New button pins
const int hiButtonPin = 7;
const int locationButtonPin = A3;
const int lightPin = 12;
int hiButtonState = 0;
int lastHiButtonState = 0;
int locationButtonState = 0;
int lastLocationButtonState = 0;
bool isLightOn = false;
void setup() {
  Serial.begin(115200);
  pinMode(locationButtonPin,
INPUT_PULLUP);
  pinMode(hiButtonPin, INPUT_PULLUP);
  pinMode(lightPin, OUTPUT);
  digitalWrite(lightPin, HIGH);
  gs.begin(9600);
}

void loop() {
  bool newData = false;
  if (millis() - del > 5000) {
    for (unsigned long start = millis(); millis() -
start < 1000;) {
      del = millis();
      while (gs.available()) {
        char c = gs.read();
        if (gps.encode(c)) // Did a new valid
sentence come in?
          newData = true;
      }
    }
  }

```

```

if (newData) {
  float flat, flon;
  unsigned long age;
  gps.f_get_position(&flat, &flon, &age);
  sflat = flat;
  sflon = flon;
  Serial.print("LAT=");
  Serial.print(flat ==
TinyGPS::GPS_INVALID_F_ANGLE ? 0.0 :
flat, 6);
  Serial.print(" LON=");
  Serial.println(flou ==
TinyGPS::GPS_INVALID_F_ANGLE ? 0.0 :
flon, 6);
}

if (millis() - tsLastReport > 3000) {
  tsLastReport = millis();
}

locationButtonState =
digitalRead(locationButtonPin);
if (locationButtonState == LOW &&
lastLocationButtonState == HIGH) {
  flag1 = 1;
  flagt = millis();
  gsm.begin(9600);
  Serial.println("Sending Location SMS");
  gsm.println("AT+CMGF=1\r");
  delay(100);
  gsm.println("AT+CMEE=1\r");
  delay(100);

  gsm.println("AT+CMGS=\"+964780*****\
\r\n");
  delay(100);
  sms1 = "Location information";

```

```

    sms = " http://maps.google.com/maps?q="
+ String(sflat, 6) + "," + String(sflon, 6);
    Serial.println(sms1);
    Serial.println(sms);
    gsm.println(sms1);
    delay(100);
    gsm.println(sms);
    delay(100);
    gsm.print((char)26);
    delay(100);
    gsm.println();
    delay(3000);
    gs.begin(9600);
    blinkLight(10, 100);
}

```

```

hiButtonState = digitalRead(hiButtonPin);
if (hiButtonState == LOW &&
lastHiButtonState == HIGH) {
    digitalWrite(lightPin, HIGH);
    isLightOn = false;
    flag1 = 1;
    flagt = millis();
    gsm.begin(9600);
    Serial.println("Sending imfine SMS");
    gsm.println("AT+CMGF=1\r");
    delay(100);
    gsm.println("AT+CMEE=1\r");
    delay(100);

gsm.println("AT+CMGS=\"+964780*****\
\r\n");
    delay(100);
    sms1 = "HI";
    Serial.println(sms1);
    gsm.print(sms1);

```

```

    delay(100);
    gsm.print((char)26);
    delay(100);
    gsm.println();
    delay(3000);
    gs.begin(9600);
}

lastHiButtonState = hiButtonState;
lastLocationButtonState =
locationButtonState;
}

void blinkLight(int numBlinks, int blinkDelay) {
    for (int i = 0; i < numBlinks; ++i) {
        digitalWrite(lightPin, HIGH);
        delay(blinkDelay);
        digitalWrite(lightPin, LOW);
        delay(blinkDelay);
    }

    isLightOn = true;
}

```

The Circuit and Test

The results obtained by the seat of fainting cases device were as follows: In the case of the person's level leaning and the person sitting beyond the normal limit, as well as in the event of many concussions, notification via the vibration sensor, the device will issue an alarm sound alerting the surrounding people of a person who has fainted the results obtained are in accordance with the experiment as shown in figure 9.

Figure 9. The Seat of Fainting Cases Device

After the Arduino Nano circuit is completed and connected to the vibration and tilt sensors, the device will send an SMS message containing the exact location of the person wearing the device, as shown in the figure 10.

Figure 10. The Result of SMS Location

In case the patient fell but is in good condition, the device contains a button that sends a text message containing the phrase “I am fine”. as show in the figure 11.

Figure 11. The SMS “I am fine”

Finally, we made box to contain the all electrical part we use show in the figure 12.

Figure 12. Final Results Design

Conclusion and Feature

The results of the design study indicate that the tilt sensor and the sensor work in a way that can be assembled using Nano and some other electronic parts. These two sensors were used to predict the falls of patients. In addition, an SMS message was sent containing the person’s location. The button that sends the SMS message was checked. It contains the word “I am fine” in order to reassure people with a message

about the location of the person who fell, but he is fine. The device is on an audio alarm for those around him. The patient has fallen. This device can be used to monitor patients who suffer from fainting frequently when their lives are normal, as the size of the device is small and can be worn with a future work belt. It includes the addition of measuring pressure, temperature, and heart rate level to give a future prediction in the event that the patient's vital signs suffer from any disorder.

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